

```

---
title: "ONE_DC_Script"
author: "Cindy Audiger"
date: "2026-07-01"
output:
  pdf_document: default
  html_document: default
---

```{r setup}
library(Seurat)
library(ggplot2)
library(dplyr)
library(ggrepel)
library(patchwork)
library(pheatmap)
library(RColorBrewer)

set.seed(42)
```

```{r parameters}
— Global parameters used throughout this script —————
CLUSTER_COL <- "NEW_CLUSTERS" # metadata column holding cluster IDs
CLUSTERS_BLOOD <- c("g4") # blood DC1
CLUSTERS_CULT <- c("g3", "g1", "g9") # culture-derived DC1
CLUSTER_NEG <- c("g11") # blood DC2
N_HVG <- 2000 # HVGs to use for correlation
OUTDIR <- "." # output directory
```

```{r load-data}
Load the Seurat object.
Replace this path with wherever the .rds lives in your data folder.
seurat_obj <- readRDS(file.path("data", "Seurat_Join_Filt_fresh_unstim.rds"))
```

```{r clustering}
seurat_obj <- FindNeighbors(seurat_obj, dims = 1:20)
seurat_obj <- FindClusters(seurat_obj, resolution = 0.5, cluster.name = CLUSTER_COL)
seurat_obj <- RunUMAP(seurat_obj, dims = 1:20, reduction.name = "umap_NEW_CLUSTERS")
```

# Panel A
```{r panel-a-umap}
DimPlot(seurat_obj, reduction = "umap_NEW_CLUSTERS") +
 theme(aspect.ratio = 1)
```

```{r panel-a-umap-save}
p <- DimPlot(
 seurat_obj,
 reduction = "umap_NEW_CLUSTERS"
)

ggsave(
 file.path(OUTDIR, "UMAP_NEW_CLUSTERS.pdf"),
 p,
 width = 6,
 height = 6
)

```

```

)
...

Supplementary figure - Panel A
```{r supplefig-a-heatmap}
DefaultAssay(seurat_obj) <- "RNA"
Idents(seurat_obj) <- CLUSTER_COL

Fresh_unstim_FindAllMarkers <- FindAllMarkers(seurat_obj, only.pos = TRUE)

saveRDS(Fresh_unstim_FindAllMarkers, file = file.path(OUTDIR,
"Fresh_unstim_FindAllMarkers.rds"))

Fresh_unstim_FindAllMarkers_TOP20 <- Fresh_unstim_FindAllMarkers %>%
  group_by(cluster) %>%
  dplyr::filter(avg_log2FC > 1) %>%
  slice_head(n = 20) %>%
  ungroup()

DoHeatmap(
  object = seurat_obj,
  assay = "RNA",
  features = Fresh_unstim_FindAllMarkers_TOP20$gene,
  group.by = CLUSTER_COL,
  size = 2
) +
  theme(
    axis.text.x = element_text(size = 15),
    axis.text.y = element_text(size = 4),
    aspect.ratio = 50 / 30
  )
...

# Panel B
```{r panel-b-featureplots}
— 1. Marker genes to plot _____
features <- c("CLEC9A", "IRF8", "CADM1", "SIRPA", "IRF4", "ITGAX", "LAMP3",
"CCR7", "MKI67", "MPO", "HBB", "CLC", "CD14", "XCR1", "CD83")

— 2. Generate individual plots _____
plot_list <- lapply(features, function(gene) {
 FeaturePlot(
 seurat_obj,
 features = gene,
 reduction = "umap_NEW_CLUSTERS",
 pt.size = 0.8,
 order = TRUE # plot expressing cells on top
) +
 scale_color_viridis_c(
 option = "viridis",
 name = "Expression",
 guide = guide_colorbar(barwidth = 0.8, barheight = 6)
) +
 labs(title = gene) +
 theme_void() +
 theme(
 plot.title = element_text(face = "bold.italic", size = 10, hjust = 0.5,
margin = margin(b = 2)),
 legend.text = element_text(size = 12),
 legend.title = element_text(size = 14),
 legend.position = "right",

```

```

 plot.margin = margin(3, 3, 3, 3),
 axis.line = element_line(colour = "black", linewidth = 0.4),
 aspect.ratio = 1
)
})

— 3. Assemble grid layout with patchwork _____
n_genes <- length(features)
n_cols <- 3
n_rows <- ceiling(n_genes / n_cols)

combined <- wrap_plots(plot_list, ncol = n_cols) +
 plot_layout(ncol = n_cols, widths = rep(1, n_cols)) +
 plot_annotation(
 title = "Marker gene expression",
 theme = theme(
 plot.title = element_text(face = "bold", size = 13, hjust = 0.5,
 margin = margin(b = 5))
)
) &
 theme(plot.margin = margin(0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2))

— 4. Save (height/width scale with grid size) _____
panel_size <- 2.8
plot_width <- n_cols * panel_size
plot_height <- n_rows * panel_size

ggsave(
 file.path(OUTDIR, "FeaturePlot_markers_2col2.pdf"),
 combined,
 width = plot_width,
 height = plot_height,
 device = "pdf"
)

cat("Saved: FeaturePlot_markers_2col2.pdf\n")
cat("Layout:", n_cols, "columns x", n_rows, "rows\n")
```



```

Supplementary figure - Panel C
```{r supplefig-c-correlation-all}
# — 1. Confirm cluster column exists _____
stopifnot(CLUSTER_COL %in% colnames(seurat_obj@meta.data))
idents(seurat_obj) <- CLUSTER_COL

all_clusters <- sort(unique(as.character(seurat_obj@meta.data[[CLUSTER_COL]])))
cat("Clusters found:", paste(all_clusters, collapse = ", "), "\n")

# — 2. Select HVGs from the normalised data _____
# VariableFeatures() works for both Seurat v4 (Assay) and v5 (Assay5)
hvg <- VariableFeatures(seurat_obj)
if (length(hvg) == 0) {
  message("No HVGs found – running FindVariableFeatures() now.")
  seurat_obj <- FindVariableFeatures(seurat_obj, nfeatures = N_HVG)
  hvg <- VariableFeatures(seurat_obj)
}
hvg <- hvg[seq_len(min(N_HVG, length(hvg)))]
cat("Using", length(hvg), "HVGs for correlation.\n")

# — 3. Compute pseudobulk average expression per cluster _____
avg_expr <- AverageExpression(

```


```

```

seurat_obj,
features = hvg,
assays = "RNA",
group.by = CLUSTER_COL,
layer = "data" # uses normalised (log1p) counts
)$RNA

avg_mat <- as.matrix(avg_expr)
colnames(avg_mat) <- as.character(colnames(avg_mat))
cat("Average expression matrix:", nrow(avg_mat), "genes x", ncol(avg_mat),
"clusters\n")

— 4. Compute Pearson correlation across clusters _____
cor_mat <- cor(avg_mat, method = "pearson")

— 5. Annotate clusters for the heatmap _____
ann_df <- data.frame(
 Population = ifelse(
 colnames(cor_mat) %in% CLUSTERS_BLOOD, "Blood DC1",
 ifelse(colnames(cor_mat) %in% CLUSTERS_CULT, "Culture DC1",
 ifelse(colnames(cor_mat) %in% CLUSTER_NEG, "Blood DC2", "Other"))
),
 row.names = colnames(cor_mat)
)

ann_colours <- list(
 Population = c(
 "Blood DC1" = "#CC79A7",
 "Culture DC1" = "#9990FF",
 "Blood DC2" = "#FF9666",
 "Other" = "#888780"
)
)

— 6. Plot full correlation heatmap (all clusters) _____
Reorder so DC1 clusters are grouped together for easier reading
dcl_clusters <- c(CLUSTERS_BLOOD, CLUSTERS_CULT, CLUSTER_NEG)
other_clusters <- setdiff(colnames(cor_mat), dcl_clusters)
col_order <- c(dcl_clusters, other_clusters)
cor_ordered <- cor_mat[col_order, col_order]

pheatmap(
 cor_ordered,
 color = colorRampPalette(c("#F5EBF0", "#CC79A7", "#663366"))(100),
 breaks = seq(0.7, 1, length.out = 101),
 annotation_col = ann_df,
 annotation_colors = ann_colours,
 annotation_row = ann_df,
 cluster_rows = TRUE,
 cluster_cols = TRUE,
 show_rownames = TRUE,
 show_colnames = TRUE,
 fontsize = 10,
 fontsize_row = 9,
 fontsize_col = 9,
 border_color = NA,
 main = "Inter-cluster transcriptional correlation (Pearson, HVGs)",
 filename = file.path(OUTDIR, "DC1_correlation_heatmap_all_clusters.pdf"),
 width = 8, height = 7
)

```

```

cat("Saved: DC1_correlation_heatmap_all_clusters.pdf\n")
```

# Panel C
```{r panel-c-correlation-focused}
Focused heatmap: DC1 clusters + Blood DC2
(dcl_clusters already includes CLUSTER_NEG from the previous chunk)
focused_clusters <- unique(c(dcl_clusters, CLUSTER_NEG))

dcl_cor <- cor_mat[focused_clusters, focused_clusters]

ann_dcl <- data.frame(
 Population = ifelse(
 focused_clusters %in% CLUSTERS_BLOOD, "Blood DC1",
 ifelse(focused_clusters %in% CLUSTERS_CULT, "Culture DC1", "Blood DC2")
),
 row.names = focused_clusters
)

ann_colours_focused <- list(
 Population = c(
 "Blood DC1" = "#CC79A7",
 "Culture DC1" = "#9990FF",
 "Blood DC2" = "#FF9666"
)
)

pheatmap(
 dcl_cor,
 color = colorRampPalette(c("#F5EBF0", "#CC79A7", "#663366"))(100),
 breaks = seq(0.7, 1, length.out = 101),
 annotation_col = ann_dcl,
 annotation_row = ann_dcl,
 annotation_colors = ann_colours_focused,
 cluster_rows = FALSE,
 cluster_cols = FALSE,
 display_numbers = TRUE,
 number_format = "%.3f",
 number_color = "black",
 fontsize = 11,
 border_color = NA,
 main = "Blood DC1, Blood DC2 & Culture DC1 - pairwise correlation",
 filename = file.path(OUTDIR, "DC1_correlation_heatmap_DC1_BloodDC2.pdf"),
 width = 6, height = 5.5
)

cat("Saved: DC1_correlation_heatmap_DC1_BloodDC2.pdf\n")
```

# Session info
```{r session-info}
sessionInfo()
```

```